

CONTROLLED VACUUM INFUSION OF HETEROGENEOUS FIBROUS PREFORMS

D. K. Modi¹, M. S. Johnson¹, A. C. Long¹, C. D. Rudd¹, F. Robitaille²

¹ *Polymer Composites Research Group and School of Mechanical, Materials and Manufacturing Engineering, University of Nottingham, Nottingham, NG7 2RD, UK.*

² *Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Ottawa, Ottawa, K1N 6N5, Canada*

SUMMARY: Low repeatability of closed moulding polymer composites manufacturing processes is mainly due to deviations in the flow patterns, from the predicted or idealised flow patterns, during the infusion stage. This, in turn, is due to the limited knowledge of, and an inability to account for, all the factors affecting the fluid flow in simulations. In this paper, it is shown that in many cases, material heterogeneity can also lead to deviating flow patterns. In light of complexities of these processes and the potential improvements offered by an online control system, a closed loop control system consisting of image acquisition, image analysis and computer controlled injection valves is proposed. The development of various stages of the system is reported and the potential of the system is demonstrated through “virtual” experiments.

KEYWORDS: LCM Processing, Vacuum Infusion, On-line Control.

INTRODUCTION

In liquid composite moulding processes, a cut preform is placed between two halves of the mould, the mould is closed and resin is injected from an injection port to infuse the preform. At the end of infusion, resin is allowed to cure and the finished part is extracted. In Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) process, resin injection can be under constant flow rate or constant pressure conditions, as both the mould halves are rigid. In Vacuum Infusion (VI) process, the negative pressure gradient created by the evacuation of air from the mould facilitates replacement of the rigid mould top half with a flexible plastic bag as well as resin infusion. Irrespective of the process, understanding of the infusion process is crucial for developing a successful and reliable mould designs. Often, the flow progression can be unintuitive and prediction of filling patterns with simulation tools is necessary [1]. The flow in liquid composite moulding processes is modelled using Darcy’s law, which uses a constitutive parameter called “permeability” to represent the resistance offered by the fibrous preform to the fluid flow through it. The permeability of a fibrous preform depends on many factors such as fibre volume fraction, preform architecture etc. and knowledge about it is important for design of a reliable mould and injection system. Various methods [2-3] of measuring the preform permeability have been reported in literature. However, disagreement in results, even for identical materials and measurement methods, highlights the limitations of these methods. Recently, consideration has been given to factors not explored previously. Material variations and sample preparation [4], fibre crimp [5], fibre tow nesting [6], etc. have been reported as being responsible for the broad distribution of permeability values. In addition, Pan et al. [7] found that the permeability values of a number of fabrics follow a normal distribution.

The variability discussed above makes fail-safe design of a mould and an injection scheme a difficult task, and development of more advanced approaches such as off-line or on-line control of the infusion process is desirable. In off-line or passive control systems, prior to the mould preparation, a set of possible flow scenarios is generated from flow advancement simulations for pre-defined values of process parameters and material properties. Then, simulation results are analyzed to arrive at an optimum arrangement of injection ports and vents to achieve maximum probability of success for the infusion process [7-13].

In on-line or active control systems, a set of sensors are used to collect information about the infusion process. In addition, the process is dynamically controlled by altering the injection parameters. These systems can be divided into two categories. In the first category of systems, prior to start of the infusion process, flow advancement simulations are performed to create a set of possible flow scenarios for pre-defined values of process parameters and material properties. During the infusion process, the information collected by the flow sensors is used to identify the closest flow scenario and to arrive at a suitable control action, which is implemented through the control hardware. In the second category, flow simulations are performed on-line during the infusion process. An optimum corrective action is chosen after analysis of simulation results, and is implemented through the control hardware.

Lee et al. [14] used a DC resistance sensor to control the infusion stage in the RTM process. The flow progression was controlled through a controller designed to regulate either the resin viscosity (by regulating the mould temperature) or the flow rate at various injection ports. However, the authors did not report the approach used for identification of flow scenarios as well as the criterion used in the selection of a corrective action. Kang et al. [15] demonstrated the use of on-line controls in the RTM process by infusing a part through sequential injection ports. The authors used flow simulations to arrive at optimum injection port locations. A photo-detector, mounted in the bottom half of the mould, monitored the arrival of the flow via a voltage change. Depending on the sensor feedback, sequential constant pressure injection ports were opened. Bickerton et al. [16], Lawrence et al. [17] used a DC point sensor while, Nielsen and Pitchumani [18] used an image acquisition system to develop an on-line control system for RTM process. In all systems, the injection was under controlled flow rate conditions and control action was taken using either genetic algorithms or neural networks. The applicability of these systems, for pressure-driven processes such as Vacuum Infusion (VI), is limited. Nielsen and Pitchumani [19] used the same system as reported in [18], with an online permeability estimator, to implement controlled injection pressure RTM infusion. This system also employed neural network, which is a proxy flow simulator. As neural networks are restricted to the range of parameters over which they are trained and their accuracy depends strongly on their design architecture [20], online flow simulations are preferable. Nielsen and Pitchumani [20] used Finite-Difference (FD) based simulation tool to perform real-time simulations for controlled flow rate infusion. However, FD based simulation tools are limited in their applicability [21].

It is clear that on-line control systems offer the highest probability of success for the infusion process. However, they are difficult to design and implement, and their success depends highly on the underlying sensor system i.e. for an efficient control system, a fast, accurate, reliable, low-cost and non-intrusive sensor system with an ability to interface with control hardware is desirable. In addition, the ability to simulate flow advancement, analyse the results and select an optimum control action, is also important.

In the first part of this paper, the influence of inherent preform heterogeneity on the local variations in permeability values, the filling patterns and on resin wastage through vent is investigated experimentally. In the second part, a novel on-line control system, utilising

online flow advancement simulations is proposed and the development of various stages of this system is reported. The potential of the system is demonstrated through virtual experiments.

HETEROGENEITY IN FIBROUS PREFORMS

To investigate the influence of preform heterogeneity on flow progression, a number of VI (a.k.a. VARTM) experiments were carried out. Six layers of continuous fibre random mat (Vetrotex Unifilo U750/450, isotropic permeability), were packed in a VI mould (rigid mould bottom half and flexible mould top half) and were infused with hydraulic oil from four corner injection ports (Figure 1). To enable comparison of flow progression between various experiments, the entire filling process was recorded with a digital camera. In addition, for any single experiment, flow progression was compared between all injection ports. In the ideal case, with no material heterogeneity, one can expect the flow pattern to be circular (around the injection ports) and uniformly moving towards the vent. However, experimental results show significant variation in both the above mentioned comparisons (Figure 2). Note that these deviations move the location of the final filling point away from vent in an unpredictable way and necessitate resin wastage through the vent for full infusion of preforms (Figure 3).

ALL DIMENSIONS ARE IN MM.

Figure 1 Schematic of the mould set-up.

Figure 2 Variation in flow progression due to preform heterogeneity. Injection is from four corner injection ports. The circular lines show idealised flow patterns for a homogeneous preform.

Figure 3 Preform heterogeneity results in uneven, unpredictable filling patterns. The resulting unfilled region, when resin reaches the vent, necessitates increased resin wastage through the vent for complete mould infusion, even in normally identical infusion experiments.

ON-LINE FLOW CONTROL WITH IMAGE ANALYSIS

The on-line control system developed in this work uses an image acquisition and analysis system to collect the information about flow progression inside a closed mould with at least one transparent side (e.g. in vacuum infusion). This information is used to define the nodal fill-factors (initial conditions) in the simulation model. With a pre-defined set of port configurations (boundary conditions) and the initial conditions, flow advancement simulations are performed. From the simulation results, a value of a cost function for each port configuration is calculated and the configuration with the least value of the cost function is relayed to the computer controlled injection valves to correct flow deviations, if any. The strategy is repeated during the entire infusion phase. Figure 4 shows a flow chart of the main steps of the system. Next, we describe the development of each individual step.

Figure 4 Flow-chart of the proposed control system.

IMAGE ACQUISITION

To reduce the overall cost of the system and for ease of real-time interfacing, a web camera is used for image acquisition. Almost all the commercially available cameras have programmable image acquisition capabilities. For this specific work, a Fire-i™ camera from Unibrain S.A. was used to continuously capture an image of the infusion phase from the top side of the mould. Images can be captured at various resolution levels and at various time intervals.

IMAGE ANALYSIS

The analysis of the captured image is performed in MATLAB™ using the native image processing toolbox. The captured image is processed to select a region of interest and to remove perspective, if any. Then, it is passed through an averaging and a high-pass filter to convert it into binary images. As the relative position of the camera with respect to the mould can vary between experiments, the entire image acquisition and analysis system is calibrated before the start of the infusion process. The calibration values are stored and are used during the infusion phase.

NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

Correia [22] analysed one-dimensional flow in RTM and VI processes and reported that the flow patterns, in both the processes, are identical in space and differ only in time. It was further reported that the results from simulations tools modelling the infusion inside a rigid mould (e.g. RTM) can be used, with an appropriate scaling factor, to model the infusion process inside a flexible mould (e.g. VI). Hence, the flow advancement simulations in this work are carried out using LIMS. LIMS is a finite element / control volume (FE/CV) based simulation tool developed at the University of Delaware, the details of which can be found elsewhere [23].

Figure 5 Definition of the nodal fill-factors in the meshed model from the captured image.

Before starting the infusion, a set of sixteen simulation models, each with isotropic homogeneous material properties and corresponding to the 16 individual permutations of the possible port configurations, is generated. Note that each port can be in either open or closed configuration. In addition, the entire mould filling is divided into a number of equal control-steps such that in each step, a pre-defined number of nodes are required to be filled. It is important to distinguish between a time-step and a control step, which is a set of number of time-steps. Then, at the start of any control step, the current flow front status in the experiment is used to describe the initial conditions (or nodal fill-factors) for all numerical

models. This is done following a pre-defined rule to calculate the nodal fill factors from the corresponding image pixel values (Figure 5). Note that more complex schemes such as calculating, for each node, the weighted average of all the pixel values in the corresponding control volume, are possible. Numerical simulations are performed to advance the flow, in all models individually, till the end of current control step.

CONTROL ALGORITHM DESIGN

To select an appropriate corrective action from all available choices, definition of a port configuration selection criterion is necessary. This involves defining a cost function. Various cost functions such as fill-time, weight ratio of resin wasted to the porous volume of the mould, distance between the centroid of an unfilled region and the vent (henceforth, called as centroid scheme) etc. were considered. The centroid scheme, with a minimum as an optimum value, was chosen as it indirectly reflects the other cost functions i.e. if the distance between the centroid of an unfilled region and the vent is minimum at any time, the filling pattern will resemble an ideal filling pattern and the mould will be filled in the shortest possible time, with minimum amount of bleeding required through the vent. Figure 6 shows the schematic of the centroid scheme. Using the simulation results, the centroid of an unfilled region and hence, the value of the cost function, is calculated for all the port configurations. The configuration with the least value of this cost function is selected as an optimum injection strategy for the next step.

Figure 6 The Centroid scheme, used to select an optimum corrective action, uses the distance between the centroid of an unfilled region and the vent as a cost function. The port configuration with the minimum value of this distance is selected for the next phase.

For example, assume that the same mould as shown in Figure 1 has to be filled in five control steps and that its meshed model has 1000 nodes. Figure 7 shows the infusion status, in the meshed model, at the end of the second control step when 400 nodes are filled. For simplicity, also assume that there are only two possible port configurations. In the first configuration, the first three injection ports are open while, in the second configuration, only the first injection port is open. Following the strategy outlined above, simulations are carried out for both port configurations to advance the flow till the end of the third control step when 600 nodes are filled. Figure 8 shows the simulation results of the flow advancement. It is clear that for the first configuration, the centroid of an unfilled region is closer to the vent than for the second configuration. Hence, the first port configuration is chosen as an optimum injection strategy for the next control-step.

Figure 7 Flow front positions, inside the mould, at the end of the second control step when 400 nodes are filled. The mould, modeled with 1000 nodes, has to be filled in five equal control-steps, such that in each control step, 200 nodes are filled.

Figure 8 Simulation results of flow advancement at the end of the third control step when 600 nodes are filled. The centroid of an unfilled region is closer to the vent for the first port configuration (a) than for the second port configuration (b).

CONTROL IMPLEMENTATION

The optimum port configuration as selected by the control algorithm is relayed to solenoid valves, which actually control resin injection. For this work, each injection port was connected to a solenoid valve (Type 6213, Burkert Contromatic) having a response time of 700 milliseconds. These solenoid valves are controlled by a computer through a digital input/output board (DAQCard DIO- 24) and control modules (SSR series) from National Instruments.

VIRTUAL EXPERIMENTS

The control scheme was validated using virtual experiments, where the mould was replaced with a virtual (meshed) model. The elements in this model were assigned random permeability values following a normal distribution. Figure 9 shows the location of the final

filling point for various numbers of control steps. It is clear that in an uncontrolled infusion, material heterogeneity can lead to a significant deviation in the flow progression from the ideal flow progression in a homogeneous material and the final filling point can be far removed from the vent. The control system is able to identify such deviations and take corrective action such that the flow converges uniformly towards the vent and the final filling point moves towards the vent.

Figure 9 The location of the final filling point in a virtual model of the mould. Due to material heterogeneity, the final filling point in an uncontrolled infusion is far removed from the vent. In controlled infusions, the control system takes corrective action, such that the flow converges uniformly towards the vent. The resulting final filling point is closer to the vent.

CONCLUSIONS

The inherent heterogeneity in fibrous preforms used in liquid composite moulding can have an unpredictable influence on the infusion process. The resulting flow patterns can deviate significantly from predictions based on homogeneous permeability data, which may lead to increased resin wastage, increased fill times and in the worst cases, to higher part rejections. As a possible solution, an actively controlled injection system, utilising a flow monitoring and analysis system and computer controlled injection ports, has been proposed. This system captures the flow information using a low-cost web-camera and processes it digitally to identify the flow front locations inside the mould. Flow advancement simulations are performed in real-time, to predict the flow behaviour and to arrive at an appropriate corrective action. This control action is implemented via computer controlled injection ports. The proposed system is validated using virtual experiments, where the actual mould is replaced with a numerical model. Numerical results from this system show that the control system is able to identify the deviations in flow patterns and steer the flow towards the vent through appropriate corrective action. A laboratory scale set-up of the system is complete and results from the experimental investigation will be reported shortly.

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